

Pakistani and Bangladeshi Expatriates in the UAE: Implications, Economic Contributions, and Geopolitical Dynamics

Overview of Expatriate Migration from Pakistan and Bangladesh to the UAE

The UAE remains a popular destination for millions of expatriates, with a large number coming from Pakistan and Bangladesh. The flow of Pakistani and Bangladeshi nationals to the UAE has been shaped by a combination of economic factors, regional geopolitics, and labor demand. These two countries have sent over **9.8 million** migrants to the UAE, contributing immensely to the country's workforce.

As of **2023**, the Pakistani expatriate population in the UAE has grown to approximately **8.5 million**, a significant increase from **1.5 million** in **2017** [Wikipedia] . This surge in Pakistani nationals is part of a larger trend of migration to Gulf countries, where there are labor shortages in sectors such as construction, healthcare, and hospitality, which are being filled by an affordable and skilled workforce from countries like Pakistan and Bangladesh.

Migration Patterns Post-2017: Key Trends and New Destinations

In recent years, Pakistani migration patterns have evolved, with new destinations coming into focus. Alongside the UAE, **Saudi Arabia** and the **United Kingdom** have experienced notable increases in Pakistani migrants:

1. **Saudi Arabia:** Saudi Arabia continues to be a major destination, with around 2 million Pakistanis moving there between 2017 and 2022 to take on labor-intensive jobs.
2. **United Kingdom:** The UK remains a popular choice for skilled Pakistani workers, especially in the healthcare and education sectors. Between 2017 and 2022, over 500,000 Pakistanis migrated to the UK, driven by family reunification policies and professional opportunities.
3. **Canada and Australia:** With a growing focus on skilled migration, countries like **Canada** and **Australia** have welcomed a significant number of Pakistanis. Between 2017 and

2022, around **300,000** Pakistanis migrated to Canada, and **150,000** moved to Australia, mainly professionals seeking better work opportunities.

Significant migration and displacement events during the past **two years** have resulted in a tremendous deal of suffering, trauma, and fatalities. Apart from the aforementioned wars in **Gaza** and **Ukraine**, millions of people have been displaced by violence in other places, including **Yemen**, the **Central African Republic**, the **Syrian Arab Republic**, and

Sudan, Ethiopia, Myanmar, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and the African Republic. In 2022 and 2023, disasters linked to climate change and weather caused widespread relocation in a number of countries, including **Bangladesh, Brazil, Colombia, China, India, Pakistan, and the Philippines**. Furthermore, strong earthquakes struck the northern **Syrian Arab Republic** and **south-east Turkey** in February 2023, killing over **50,000** people. Many people had been rendered homeless in the **Syrian Arab Republic** by March, while an estimated **2.7 million** individuals had been displaced in **Turkey**. [【IOM】](#)

Data from Pakistan's Migration Report 2024

According to **Pakistan Migration Report 2024** from GIDS, migration trends between 2019 and 2023 have been influenced by several key factors:

- The **outflow of Pakistani migrants** declined dramatically during the Covid-19 pandemic, with numbers dropping from approximately **625,000** in 2019 to **less than 300,000** in 2020-2021. Migration saw a notable increase, with 832,000 and 862,000 migrants departing in 2022 and 2023, respectively, as pandemic restrictions were lifted [【GIDS Report, 2024】](#) .

- **Saudi Arabia** continues to be the primary destination, hosting around 50% of all Pakistani migrants in 2023, while the UAE regained its position, accounting for 27% of total migration 【GIDS Report, 2024】 .
- A significant portion of Pakistani labor migrants remains **unskilled** or **low-skilled**, with **56%** of all migrants in 2023 categorized as such 【GIDS Report, 2024】 .

The Role of Remittances in the Economies of Pakistan and Bangladesh

Remittances from Pakistani expatriates, especially those in the UAE, play a vital role in providing foreign exchange. In **2023**, Pakistan received over **\$5 billion** in remittances from the UAE, while Bangladesh benefited from over **\$3 billion** 【World Bank, 2023】 . These funds are essential for the livelihoods of millions of families in both nations and contribute to economic stability.

However, the growth of remittances has slowed in recent years. The **Pakistan Migration Report 2024** indicates a significant decline in remittance growth during **2022-2023**, with a drop of **12.6%** 【GIDS Report, 2024】 . This downturn is linked to various factors, including challenging economic conditions, the depreciation of the Pakistani rupee, and an increasing disparity between official and market exchange rates, which has led to a rise in the use of unofficial remittance channels 【GIDS Report, 2024】 .

Irregular Migration and Its Implications

Irregular migration has become an escalating concern for both Pakistan and its host countries, particularly in **Europe**. Pakistanis rank among the top ten nationalities entering Europe through illegal **land and sea routes**. In **2022**, more than **40,000** Pakistanis were reported to be illegally residing in Europe 【GIDS Report, 2024】 . Despite government initiatives aimed at reducing irregular migration, it remains a pressing issue, underscoring the dangers faced by many migrants who take unsafe routes in pursuit of better opportunities.

Pakistani Migrants in Europe

According to the **2020 International Migrant Stock**, compiled by UNDESA, approximately **952,993** Pakistani nationals resided in Europe in **2020**. Of this number, **58%** were male, and **42%** were female. The distribution of Pakistani migrants across European countries is as follows:

- **United Kingdom: 537,047** Pakistani nationals (Male: **282,645**, Female: **254,402**)
- **Germany: 79,227** Pakistani nationals (Male: **53,993**, Female: **25,234**)
- **Italy: 124,800** Pakistani nationals (Male: **89,557**, Female: **35,243**)
- **France: 27,203** Pakistani nationals (Male: **16,341**, Female: **10,862**)
- **Norway: 21,140** Pakistani nationals (Male: **10,853**, Female: **10,287**)
- **Sweden: 16,597** Pakistani nationals (Male: **9,891**, Female: **6,706**)
- **Greece: 8,823** Pakistani nationals (Male: **4,435**, Female: **4,388**)
- **Belgium: 13,246** Pakistani nationals (Male: **8,143**, Female: **5,103**) [[IOM](#)] .

The **UN Migration Report** indicates that Europe has become a key destination for Pakistani nationals in search of better economic prospects, with the **UK, Germany, and Italy** ranking as the top three host countries for these migrants. The gender distribution underscores the significant presence of male workers in Europe, mirroring labor migration patterns seen in the UAE and other Gulf nations [[IOM](#) May 2024] .

Comparison with Indian Expats in the UAE

In contrast, the **Indian** expatriate population in the UAE is approximately 3.5 million (UAE Ministry of Economy, 2023) [[GMI](#) December 2024]. Although India's expatriate community is the largest single nationality group in the UAE, the combined total of **9.8 million** Pakistanis and Bangladeshis surpasses the Indian expatriates by more than **6 million**. This demographic change highlights the growing significance of the Pakistani and Bangladeshi communities within the UAE's labor market.

Geopolitical Dynamics and Migration Governance

The **Pakistan Migration Report 2024** also points out the necessity for **policy reforms** to manage migration effectively. The country's **Emigration Ordinance** from **1979** is significantly outdated, and a draft policy document has been pending approval for over three years [[GIDS](#)

Report, 2024. The lack of a clear policy has created inefficiencies in managing labor migration and ensuring migrant welfare.

Pakistan's dependence on remittances from expatriates also fuels **geopolitical dynamics**, particularly in its relations with Gulf countries. The **UAE**, as one of the largest recipients of Pakistani labor, plays a key role in shaping Pakistan's economic policies, particularly those regarding labor migration. Migration trends in the Gulf region, particularly towards the UAE, are closely linked to the current economic and political situation in Pakistan. **Migration to Other Gulf Countries**

The **GIDS Report** indicates that the **affluent Gulf nations** remain the primary destination for Pakistani workers, drawing over **90%** of all migrants in **2022-2023**. Over the past ten years, **Saudi Arabia** and the **UAE** have been the leading destinations for Pakistani labor migrants, with Saudi Arabia historically attracting a larger number. In **2022**, Saudi Arabia accounted for **61.9%** of all Pakistani outflows, while the UAE represented **15.4%**. This pattern continued into 2023, with Saudi Arabia receiving **49.5%** of the total migrant outflows, and the UAE experiencing a notable rise to **26.7%** [GIDS Report, 2024].

Despite Pakistan's attempts to broaden migration options, such as increasing outflows to **Malaysia**, the majority of labor migrants still choose **Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries**, with **Qatar** and **Bahrain** capturing smaller portions [GIDS Report, 2024] .

Conclusion: The Future of Migration from Pakistan and Bangladesh

The ongoing migration of Pakistanis and Bangladeshis to the UAE is expected to increase, driven by the economic needs and geopolitical dynamics of both countries. This migration trend also brings to light significant challenges, including irregular migration and the increasing brain drain from Pakistan.

To ensure that this migration remains sustainable and advantageous for both Pakistan and the UAE, it is essential for Pakistan to develop a comprehensive migration policy. This policy should not only manage outflows but also respond to the rising demand for skilled labor. Additionally, enhancing efforts to tackle irregular migration and boosting remittance inflows through official channels will be vital for Pakistan's long-term economic health.

As the population of Pakistani and Bangladeshi expatriates in the UAE grows, it will be crucial to assess the socio-economic effects of these communities, particularly concerning labor market trends, remittance patterns, and political ties with the Gulf region.

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